

DENTAL FLUOROSIS FROM DRINKING WATER CONSUMPTION IN LANGTANG TOWN, PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The study area is defined by latitudes 9° 00' and 9° 15' N and longitudes 9° 45' and 9° 50' E; with approximately an average population of 300,000 inhabitants. The area is faced with problem of water supply especially during the dry season, when they resort to scanty supplies from hand – dug wells and streams. The aim of the study was to determine how drinking water has contributed towards dental fluorosis in Langtang town and environs. Fifteen (15) water samples were picked from various water sources and determined for their fluoride contents. The ion chromatographic analyzer ICA model was used. Fluoride concentration ranges from 0.11 to 6.62 mg/l, with the wells having the highest and the stream having the lowest of 0.11mg/l. Over 74% of the water in the study area has fluoride concentration above the World Health Organisation (WHO) standard limits of 1.5mg/l and 26% below the limits. Fluoride is probably being leached from fluoride bearing minerals (biotite, fluorite, hornblende, topaz, etc) from the host rock (migmatite gneiss, rhyolite) since they constitutes over 90% of the geology of the study area. Questionnaire results revealed that 23.75% of the respondent do not show evidence of mottled teeth because they were not born in the area. Some 76.25% of those born in the study area show evidence of mottled teeth. The greater numbers of respondents with mottled teeth however, fall within the age 1 to 20 years of age. About 76% of the interviewed respondents, who showed evidence of dental fluorosis, could not ascertain the cause (s) nor proffer solution to the problem. Those with mottled teeth find it difficult to chew with them as they are susceptible to breakage. Most teenagers, especially girls are often shy of the coloured teeth

KEY WORDS: Dental fluorosis, Mottledteeth, Skeletal fluorosis, Susceptible, Aquifer, Osteopathic outgrowth.

INTRODUCTION

Fluoride is found in rocks, plants, animals, air, and water in varying concentrations. The element fluorine is highly reactive and because of its reactivity, it exists in the ionic form as fluoride. It enters the human body by ingestion, inhalation and in extreme cases through the skin. Fluoride absorbed into the body, if not excreted can cause teeth mottling (dental fluorosis) or on prolonged exposure to high levels of fluoride, skeletal fluorosis may result (Hui, 1985).

Mild mottled teeth may have little public health significance, apart from causing embarrassment to the affected. It may however, bring about excessive wearing of the teeth and difficulty in mastication (Hui, 1985). Severe fluorosis makes teeth more susceptible to dental caries. In skeletal fluorosis, the skeleton increases in density and osteophytic outgrowth appears on the long bones, vertebrae, and ribs

Langtang town is situated at the southern part of the Jos Plateau, situated between the Pre- Cambrian Basement Complex rocks and the Cretaceous sedimentary rocks of the middle Benue Trough. It is defined by latitudes 9° 00' and 9° 15' N and longitudes 9° 45' and 9° 50' E. Langtang has approximately an average population of 300,000 inhabitants. The town and its environs are faced with great challenges of water supply especially during the dry season. Women and children travel long distances to obtain water for household uses. To alleviate this problem the Federal Government in collaboration with the Plateau State Government constructed two large dams with one serving as a feeder to the other. The construction of these dams did not solve the problem of water supply in the area as it is not fully in operation and appears to be inadequate. The inhabitants still rely on groundwater from hand dug wells and streams as a major source of water supply for drinking and other

household uses. Cases of teeth mottling has been reported in the area and other related areas in the northeastern parts of Nigeria with severe fluorosis index among all categories of age groups (Wongdem *et al*, 2001; Dibal and Lar, 2005; Lar, *et al*, 2007). The aim of this work is to;

1. determine the concentration of fluoride in the natural water system of the area
2. determine how drinking water has contributed towards the development of dental fluorosis in Lantang town and its environs
3. the perception of the inhabitants towards teeth mottling

GEOLOGY AND HYDROGEOLOGY

Langtang town in Langtang North Local Government area where the study was undertaken is situated on the Precambrian basement rocks. The area is comprised of migmatites, granite gneiss (basement rocks), biotite granite (Younger Granites), rhyolite and plugs of mafic rocks and pegmatites all intruding into the basement unit, which constitutes over 60% of the area. The migmatite gneiss forms the lower plains, underlying the entire area while, the granite gneiss rhyolite and the biotite granite forms the higher grounds reaching heights of about 600 to 800 meters above sea level. There is no particular trend to show that they were (biotite granite) formed in the same way as that of the Jos Plateau (ring dykes) but occur as stocks. Situated between the granite gneiss and the migmatite gneiss are massive bodies of rhyolite rocks trending in the NE – SW direction. They are fine grained rocks with quartz and feldspars as the major minerals. They melted the granite gneiss as portion of it were found in their matrix as xenoliths.

HYDROGEOLOGY

The Bapkwai stream is the the major stream that drains the entire Langtang area. It is flooded in the rainy season and dries up during the dry season. During the dry season the sands are scooped before water could be obtained. Two aquifer systems occur in this area; the weathered overburden aquifer and the fractured aquifer. The weathered overburden aquifer is variable in thickness mostly in the range of 10 to 15 meters thick and the fractured aquifer is between 25 - 30 meters thick. Water levels almost come to the surface during the rainy season but begin to go down as soon as the rain is over. As at the time of the study, there was no available record about the yield of the two aquifers, but yield may probably be in the range of 1 – 2 l/s

METHODOLOGY

Water samples were collected from wells, streams and dams in two plastic containers of 2 liters capacity each in December 2006 and January 2007. Waters from stream were sampled upstream, middle and downstream. The conductivity, pH, temperature of each water sample were measured on the spot, using temperature/conductivity meter (Oakton pH 5/6) under hygienic condition. Depths to water in wells were determined using a steel tape. Questionnaires were also administered to respondent at the Junior Secondary School Langtang and the Local Government Secretariat. Random observations of teeth mottling were also carried out on children ages between 1 to 11 in Langtang Town and its environs.

SAMPLE PREPARATION AND ANALYSIS

The cations magnesium, calcium, potassium and sodium were analysed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (A.A.S) with the lowest detection limit of 0.01 ppm and titration method for the anions (chloride, sulphate bicarbonate and carbonate).The anion (F⁻) was determined using an ion chromatographic analyzer (ICA) a product of Yokogawa - Japan equipped with conductivity and UV detectors. The method of the ion chromatographic analyzer is described by (Ubom and Tsuchiya, 1988).

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the levels of dissolved constituents in the study area. Table 2 is the results of observation made on respondent and Table 3 shows the methods of water storage practiced by the inhabitants. Fig 1 shows the geology of the area and sampling points. Fluoride concentration ranges from 0.11 to 6.62 mg/l, with the wells having the highest and the stream having the lowest of 0.11mg/l (Table 1). On the average over 74% of the water in the study area has fluoride concentration above the World Health Organisation (WHO 2004) standard limits of 1.5mg/l and 26% below the limits. From questionnaire results and observation carried out randomly on children between age 1 to 11 years, teenagers between the ages of 11 and 20 years at the Government Day

Secondary School Langtang and workers at the Local Government Secretariat totaling 181 persons, results revealed that 23.75% of the respondents do not show evidence of mottled teeth because they were not born in the study area. Whereas the remaining 76.25% who were all born in the study area all show evidence of mottled teeth. The greater number of respondents with mottled teeth however, falls within the age 1 to 20 with each having 96.6% and 87.7 % of dental fluorosis respectively. 61.5% of the respondents store their water in clay pot, 34.3% in plastic containers and 4.1% in steel containers.

Table 2: Observation of teeth mottling among respondents.

Age Limit	1-10	11-20	21 above
Number observed	24	71	86
Number given birth to in the study area	23	56	46
Number with no dental fluorosis	2	9	32
Number with dental fluorosis	22	62	54
% of people with dental fluorosis	91.6%	87.3%	62.7%

Table3: Water storage method in the study area

Storage material	Frequency	Percentage
Clay pot	104	61.5%
Plastic containers	58	34.3%
Steel containers	7	4.1%

DISCUSSION

Fluoride concentration, Water Consumption and Geology

Results of the study indicates that groundwater is used for cooking and drinking especially during the raining season since it is perceived to be purer (due to low turbidity) than surface water (stream or dam water, which tend to be highly turbid), which is used for cleaning and washing. Some households use alum to remove turbidity in their drinking water without knowing that alum treatment has been found to decrease fluoride concentration in water (Njenga, 1982). Boiling of drinking water is practiced by some inhabitants of the area to disinfect the water of microbial contamination. However, boiling has no effect on the levels of fluoride in the water. It has earlier been reported that fluoride levels in the streams are higher than any other source of water supply in the area ((Wongdem *et al*, 2002). However, the present study is at variance with these findings as the groundwater is found to contain more fluoride than the surface water. This is possible because interaction between groundwater and fluoride bearing minerals is enhanced as the water moves within the host rock. The surface water will obviously contain lower fluoride because of dilution from rainfall during the rainy season. Fluoride is probably being leached from fluoride bearing minerals (biotite, fluorite, hornblende, topaz etc) from the host rock (migmatite gneiss and rhyolite) since they constitutes over 90% of the geology of the study area. Although, the wells dry up in the dry season, interactions with the inhabitants revealed that dependence on the groundwater sources (wells) is more than the surface water which incidentally has more fluoride.

Fluoride consumption and dental fluorosis

Results from the administered questionnaires and random examination of teeth of children in the study area revealed that 76% of the inhabitants suffer from dental fluorosis (91% of the children are within the age 1-10, 87.3% within age 11-20 and 62.7% of people within the age of 21 and above). This has correlated positively to

the facts that, all the individual that have dental fluorosis were all born in the area and were exposed to high levels of fluoride from childhood.

It was also observed during the study that there are children and adults who, though they were born and raised in the area do not show any evidence of dental fluorosis. Such individuals may be protected by genetic predisposition, or by other environmental factors. (Ekstrand and Ehrebebo, 1979).

Methods of water storage

Investigation showed that clay pots were the best containers for reducing fluoride in drinking water, with the greatest reduction occurring after 5 days of storage (Wilkister *et al*, 2001). It is presumed that fluoride gets absorbed on to the sites of the clay minerals contained in the pottery material. This study did not determine whether there is need for regeneration of the absorption capacities of the pots after repeated usage. In spite of the high usage of these pots for water storage, evidences of dental fluorosis in quite a good number of the inhabitants were observed, other water storage containers used in the region (plastic and steel containers) are not known to reduce the fluoride content of the drinking water and only few respondents use it

Perception of respondents to dental fluorosis

About 76% of the interviewed respondents, who show evidence of dental fluorosis, could not ascertain the cause (s) nor proffer solution to the problem. The study also revealed that those with mottled teeth find it difficult to chew with them as they are susceptible to breakage. Most teenagers especially girls are often shy of the coloured teeth

CONCLUSION

From the foregoing it can be concluded that drinking water has contributed greatly towards the development of dental fluorosis in Langtang town and environs. With 74% of the water having fluoride concentration above the World Health Organization limits, which incidentally is the water the inhabitants directly depends on, it has correlated well with the number of people with dental fluorosis.

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Table 1: Dissolved constituents in the study area

	Bapkwai	Katang	Bangon	Makong	Pajat 1	Pajat 2	Shishiri	Pajat 3	Pajat 4	Bapkwai 2	Bakin Kogi	Pajat 5	Konkong	Gunung 1
Location	1													
Source	Stream	Well	Dam	Dam	Well	Well	Well	Well	Well	Stream	Well	Well	Well	Stream
Date of sampling	7/12/2006	7/12/2006	8/12/2006	8/12/2006	8/12/2006	9/12/2006	9/12/2006	9/12/2006	9/12/2006	13/12/2006	13/12/2006	13/12/2006	13/12/2006	16/01/2006
Parameters														
Conductivity(MV)	21	17	60	23	18	23	17	16	14	24	21	18	24	22
Temperature (o C)	26.5	31.1	27.2	26.1	33	31.2	32.7	33.8	33.7	31	28.5	33	32.4	31
pH	7.46	7.38	8.31	8.01	7.69	7.77	7.06	7.78	7.41	7.68	7.56	7.59	7.34	7.5
Calcium (Mg/l)	17.7	18.34	6.31	6.01	18.04	15.72	7.98	20.68	31.35	14.42	17.18	18.04	17.47	–
Magnesium	6.04	10.48	2.6	2.27	8.21	11.54	1.27	13.91	14.1	4.92	6.04	8.2	4.91	–
Sodium	42.5	94.99	20.74	20.5	83.23	101.7	28.53	99.26	117.5	29.23	42.49	83.23	48.88	–
Potassium	1.16	1.77	0.6	0.2	0.47	0.04	ND	0.64	48.2	0.89	1.15	0.46	ND	–
Bicarbonate	280	427	122	110.8	293	403	85.4	433.1	329.4	207.4	280	292.8	195.2	–
Sulfate	ND	16.5	ND	ND	4.12	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	4.12	ND	–
Chloride	7.1	7.1	7.1	7.1	28.4	24.82	18	28.4	7.1	7.09	7.09	28.36	35.46	–
Fluoride	1.23	1.25	1.45	1.24	2.21	6.62	1.76	6.18	4.41	0.11	1.23	2.21	2.94	2.22
Carbonate	6.5	6	6	6	6	6	6	9	12	12	6.5	6	6	–